

Viscosity of Magnesium Bromide, Sodium Sulphate, and Calcium Chloride in Dioxane-water Mixtures

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Viscosities of magnesium bromide, sodium sulphate, and calcium chloride solutions in 10, 20, and 30% dioxane-water mixtures have been studied at 35°. The viscosity data fit well with the modified form of the Jones-Dole equation. The constant 'B' is found to depend on the composition of the solvent. The additive character of 'B' is not noticed.

Viscosities of magnesium bromide, sodium sulphate, and calcium chloride solutions in 10, 20, and 30% dioxane-water mixtures have been studied at 35° with a view to testing the applicability of the modified form of the Jones-Dole equation, suggested previously¹, and also to ascertaining the additive character of the constant 'B' of the equation, as suggested by Cox and Wolfenden².

EXPERIMENTAL

Magnesium bromide used was of E. Merck E.P. quality and sodium sulphate was of E. Merck G.R. variety. Calcium chloride solution was prepared by adding dilute hydrochloric acid slowly to calcium carbonate till a little CaCO_3 was left undissolved. The above solution was filtered and from it a stock solution was prepared. The Mg^{2+} , SO_4^{2-} , and Ca^{2+} contents were analysed by standard methods³. Preparation of the solvents and solutions and measurements of viscosity and conductance were the same as described earlier⁴.

TABLE I

Conc.	10% Dioxane η/η_0		20% Dioxane η/η_0		30% Dioxane η/η_0	
	Obs.	Calc.	Obs.	Calc.	Obs.	Calc.
	A. MgBr_2 .					
0.1000M	1.0512	1.0515	1.0695	1.0689	1.0829	1.0839
0.0750	1.0383	1.0391	1.0522	1.0526	1.0603	1.0610
0.0500	1.0260	1.0267	1.0362	1.0360	1.0426	1.0460
0.0250	1.0140	1.0140	1.0185	1.1900	1.0217	1.0213
0.0100	1.0062	1.0061	1.0084	1.0084	1.0093	1.0098
0.0075	1.0052	1.0047	1.0071	1.0065	1.0074	1.0077
0.0050	1.0043	1.0034	1.0047	1.0044	1.0064	1.0068
0.0025	1.0028	1.0019	1.0032	1.0025	1.0027	1.0036

1. Patnaik and Das, *Curr. Sci.*, 1956, 25, 337.
2. *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1934, 145A, 475.
3. Vogel, "Text Book of Quantitative Analysis".
4. Acharya *et al.*, *this Journal*, 1957, 24, 56.

TABLE I (contd.).

Conc.	10% Dioxane η/η_0		20% Dioxane η/η_0		30% Dioxane η/η_0	
	Obs.	Calc.	Obs.	Calc.	Obs.	Calc.
B. Na_2SO_4 .						
0.1000 M	1.0341	1.0342	1.0300	1.0380	1.0460	1.0461
0.0760	1.0263	1.0341	1.0201	1.0201	1.0373	1.0368
0.0500	1.0180	1.1800	1.0200	1.0201	1.0280	1.0288
0.0260	1.0086	1.0086	1.0100	1.0108	1.0134	1.0135
0.0100	1.0041	1.0043	1.0047	1.0047	1.0061	1.0061
0.0076	1.0032	1.0055	1.0038	1.0030	1.0047	1.0048
0.0050	1.0024	1.0025	1.0028	1.0028	1.0035	1.0034
0.0025	1.0013	1.0015	1.0012	1.0016	1.0018	1.0019
C. CaCl_2 .						
0.1000	1.0380	1.0376	1.0452	1.0455	1.0545	1.0542
0.0760	1.0284	1.0287	1.0350	1.0348	1.0412	1.0416
0.0500	1.0197	1.0107	1.0240	1.0238	1.0292	1.0287
0.0250	1.0103	1.0104	1.0123	1.0126	1.0151	1.0153
0.0100	1.0051	1.0057	1.0055	1.0055	1.0071	1.0070
0.0076	1.0033	1.0037	1.0041	1.0045	1.0051	1.0055
0.0050	1.0030	1.0027	1.0033	1.0031	1.0035	1.0037
0.0025	1.0012	1.0015	1.0014	1.0017	1.0021	1.0022

TABLE II

Solvent comp.	Magnesium bromide.		Sodium sulphate.		Calcium chloride.	
	$A \times 10^2$.	X.	$A \times 10^2$.	X.	$A \times 10^2$.	X.
10%	1.43	1.00	1.34	1.00	1.45	1.00
20	1.45	0.97	1.52	0.99	1.45	0.99
30	1.55	1.04	1.80	0.98	1.55	0.92

TABLE III

Solv. comp.	B		ΔB	B		ΔB	B		ΔB
	MgBr_2 .	BaBr_2 .	(MgBr_2 - BaBr_2).	Na_2SO_4 .	K_2SO_4 .	(Na_2SO_4 - K_2SO_4)	CaCl_2 .	BaCl_2 .	(CaCl_2 - BaCl_2).
10%	0.460	0.284	0.176	0.300	0.280	0.020	0.330	0.250	0.100
20	0.600	0.440	0.160	0.325	0.300	0.025	0.400	0.405	0.005
30	0.870	0.675	0.195	0.410	0.380	0.030	0.460	0.648	0.188

DISCUSSION

The relative viscosities of MgBr_2 , Na_2SO_4 , and CaCl_2 in different solvent compositions (wt.% of dioxane) were directly determined. The Jones-Dole equation has been found to hold good for 10% solvent composition for all the three electrolytes, but is inadequate for 20% and 30% solvent compositions. These are, however, satisfactorily represented by the modified form¹:

$$\eta/\eta_0 = 1 + A\sqrt{C} + BC^2.$$

The values of 'A' and 'X' for the three electrolytes are recorded in Table II. In Table III, the values of 'B' along with the 'B' values for barium bromide⁵, potassium sulphate⁶, and barium chloride⁵ are tabulated. The relative viscosities were calculated by these determined values of 'B' and 'X'. The calculated and the observed values are in good agreement for the range of concentrations of the solute. 0.100*M* to 0.0025*M* investigated at 10, 20, and 30% solvent compositions. The data are recorded in Table I.

Cox and Wolfenden² from the study of the pair of electrolytes, KCl - NaCl and KNO₃ - NaNO₃, have found that the difference in the values of 'B' of such pairs is connected with the difference in the individual character of the sphere of solvation of the cation and the anion. It has already been suggested that in a mixed solvent⁴, the number of molecules of each species constituting the sphere of solvation depends not only on the character of the ion but also on the specific properties of both kind of molecules present in the solvent. In a pair of electrolytes, like MgBr₂ - BaBr₂, the additive character of 'B' from medium to medium can be expected only when the sphere of solvation of Mg and Ba are equally affected. Table III shows that the value *B* (ΔB) is not same for the pair MgBr₂ - BaBr₂ at 10, 20, and 30% solvent compositions. The same behaviour is also noticed for the other two pairs, Na₂SO₄ - K₂SO₄ and CaCl₂ - BaCl₂. This shows that the sphere of solvation of Mg²⁺ and Ba²⁺, Na⁺ and K⁺, and Ca²⁺ and Ba²⁺ are not equally affected and hence the additive character of 'B' is not noticed.

Pertinently, the cation shows preferential treatment to one kind of molecules, possibly water, in ordering the orientation in the second layer and this orientation need not be the same even though the charge of the two ions in question may be the same. Therefore, when the dioxane and water contents of the solvent are changed, the two ions orient the available water and dioxane molecules in different proportions and it is not surprising to find the additive relation of 'B' breaks in mixed solvent.

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5. Das and Patnaik, *this Journal*, 1962, 36, 13.

6. *Idem*, *ibid.*, 1960, 37, 682.